

Reaction of BG367-3 to major insect pests and diseases. Tirur, India, 1982-86.

Entry	Maturity (d)	Damage ^a											
		RTV	Bl	Brown spot	Sheath rot	Grain discoloration	Gall midge	Hispa	Green leafhopper	Stem borer		Yield LF (t/ha)	
										Deadheart	Whiteheads		
BG367-3	115	3	1	4	5	5	3	3	3	3	3	3	5.1
IR36	120	5	3	7	5	5	7	3	7	9	5	9	5.5
IR50	115	7	9	5	5	5	5	3	5	9	7	9	6.3
TKM9	115	8	9	5	5	5	5	3	9	9	7	9	5.6
ADT36	115	8	2	5	5	5	7	5	7	9	7	9	4.4
PY3	115	4	3	5	7	7	5	5	3	9	5	9	4.5
TN1 (susceptible check)	125	8	5	5	9	9	7	5	9	9	9	9	4.2

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice. 1-9 scale.

green leafhopper (GLH), and stem borers (SB) (see table). It has good yield potential.

The highly popular IR50 and TKM9 are severely damaged by Bl during

navarai (Dec-Apr). TKM9, recommended for sornavari (Apr-Aug), also was heavily damaged by RTV in 1984-85. IR50 is highly susceptible to LF and SB in early

samba (Jul-Nov).

BG367-3 is now under multilocation trials in Tamil Nadu and is being used in breeding for insect and disease resistance at Tirur. □

Resistance of IR varieties to leafhoppers and planthoppers

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We evaluated 25 IR varieties for resistance to rice green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*, brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera*. Pregerminated seeds were sown in rows in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with Ptb 33 as the resistant check and TN1 the susceptible check. Each variety had five replications. At 7 d after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 20 per variety and infested with 7-8 1st-instar nymphs of BPH and WBPH and 5 2d-instar GLH nymphs per seedling. When the susceptible check died, test varieties were rated for damage by the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)*.

Levels of resistance to GLH, BPH, and WBPH differed significantly. IR62 and IR64 exhibited high resistance to all three hopper species (see table). IR28, IR52, IR54, IR56, IR58, IR62,

Reactions of IR varieties to leafhoppers and planthoppers.

Variety	Damage rating ^a					
	GLH		BPH		WBPH	
IR5	6.6	e	5.4	d	5.4	d
IR8	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR20	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR22	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR24	5.4	d	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR26	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR28	1.0	a	5.4	d	5.4	d
IR29	6.2	e	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR30	5.4	d	9.0	f	6.2	d
IR32	3.4	c	9.0	f	5.4	d
IR34	3.0	bc	9.0	f	5.4	d
IR36	2.6	b	6.6	e	5.0	c
IR38	5.4	d	9.0	f	6.6	e
IR40	6.6	e	6.6	e	6.6	e
IR42	2.6	b	5.2	d	5.0	c
IR46	6.6	e	4.6	c	5.4	d
IR48	2.6	b	3.4	b	3.0	b
IR50	3.4	c	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR52	1.0	a	2.6	b	1.4	a
IR54	1.0	a	6.6	e	2.6	b
IR56	1.4	a	3.4	b	2.6	b
IR58	1.0	a	5.4	d	3.4	b
IR60	3.4	c	5.4	d	5.4	d
IR62	1.0	a	1.4	a	1.4	a
IR64	1.0	a	1.0	a	1.0	a
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	1.0	a	1.0	a	1.0	a
TN1 (susceptible check)	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f

^aMean of 5 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. Damage rating is based on the SES 0-9 scale.

and IR64 were highly resistant to GLH; IR5, IR36, IR42, IR46, and

IR60 were moderately resistant to all three species. □